

A Note on Making Steel in a Basic Lined Converter from Indian Pig Iron at Mysore Iron & Steel Works.

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Indian pig iron and consequently cast iron is unfit for either acid or basic standard practice.

Comparison of Analyses.

	T.C.	Si.	Mn.	S.	P.
American pig iron for acid practice.	3'50-4'25	1'0-2'0	'40-'80	'02-'07	Max..0'1
Continental pig iron for basic practice.	3'5-4'25	'2-1	'30-2'0	'02-'20	1'75-3'0
Indian pig iron reduced with charcoal or high phosphorus coke.	3'50-4'25	As desired.	As desired.	'03	'12-'40

The comparison of analyses clearly shows that due to high phosphorus, Indian pig iron is absolutely unsuitable for making steel in an acid converter, while in order to make pig iron suitable for the basic converter, we have to raise the phosphorus by at least 1'25%. This can only be accomplished either by adding ferro-phosphorus to the metal or phosphate rock to the blast furnace burden. High cost of ferro-phosphorus makes its addition absolutely prohibitive. So far the phosphate rock is not available in India in a sufficiently large quantity to warrant its use in the blast furnace in the manufacture of high phosphorus basic pig iron for basic Bessemer steel.

Practically all the foundries in India import acid pig iron from foreign countries at a great transportation cost. In India the steel castings are made by the acid converter, the electric furnace and the acid open-hearth processes. Consequently the cost of steel castings is very high. The result is that, whenever possible, some of the large users of steel castings in India have found it cheaper to import them from foreign countries rather than to buy them from Indian foundries.

Commercial steel in India for rolling and forging purposes is made by two processes, the open-hearth and the Duplex. In the open-hearth furnaces steel is made by melting a suitable mixture of steel scrap and pig iron, say in the ratio of 50:50 and removing the

impurities through the agency of ore, flame, mill scale, limestone, etc. In the Duplex process silicon, manganese and carbon are eliminated in an acid converter, while phosphorus is got rid of in a basic open hearth furnace. Both these processes are far more expensive than the basic converter employed in Belgium and Germany to make cheap steel. The result is that Indian manufacturers have not been able to compete with foreign manufacturers who can afford to undersell their products in India.

Proposed new Method of Making Steel in India.

Depending upon the capacity of the converter, certain amount of cupola metal or direct blast furnace metal is collected in a ladle and then poured into the basic-lined converter to which a certain amount of burnt lime and mill scale have been previously added to neutralise the extra amount of silica formed from the oxidation of the silicon in the charge and at the same time produce highly oxidising basic slag, so essential for the removal of phosphorus. The blast is then applied and the metal blown as per standard acid practice. The main difference between this and the regular basic practice is that no afterblow is required for the oxidation and removal of phosphorus. The silicon and manganese contained in the charge produce high enough temperature for casting purposes. At the end of the blow the requisite amount of recarburisers and deoxidisers in the form of ferro-manganese and ferro-silicon are added to bring up the analysis to the required specification.

America and Europe have not considered the possibilities of the above-mentioned process, because the iron in the former country is sufficiently low in phosphorus while in the latter the iron is high enough in phosphorus for acid and basic practices respectively. Moreover, in Europe, the tendency is to use as high phosphorus pig iron as possible because they can employ the basic converter slag in the manufacture of agricultural fertilisers.

Author's successful Demonstration of the above Process at the Mysore Iron and Steel works, Bhadravati.

At the Mysore Iron Works they are making steel in a basic-lined baby converter, using direct charcoal blast furnace iron (.12% P) or cupola metal (.14-.15% P) and most successfully are reducing the phosphorus to .026% in the best and .066% in the worst blows.

The magnesite lining employed in basic converter has stood very well. No mill scale is used. In several heats even the addition of burnt lime has been omitted. The best results have been obtained with the following analysis.

Si	...	2·20%	S	...	·04%
Mn	...	·75%	P	...	·15%

The ingots forge very well. It is almost sure that even 30 to 40% phosphorus Indian acid pig iron can be blown successfully in a basic converter and phosphorus obtained within the Government specification for tinbar, mild steel, rail stock, etc., thereby effecting a great saving in the price per ton of steel manufactured in India in a basic converter using ordinary high phosphorus Indian pig iron. The silicon and manganese content of the metal used for blowing can be exactly the same as used for acid practice. As stated previously, the blow is handled similar to acid practice and absolutely no afterblow, whatsoever, is required.

Advantages of the Process.

- (1) Making of cheap converter instead of costly electric or open-hearth furnace steel castings and ingots.
- (2) Indian low phosphorus cast iron or pig iron made fit for basic blowing.
- (3) No afterblow and consequently no danger of over-oxidising the metal.
- (4) Small initial investment with high production at low cost.
- (5) Independent of foreign costly acid pig iron for steel making, specially castings.
- (6) Tremendous saving in steel ingots and castings made by this process as compared to other costly processes at present employed in the country.

